

A STUDY ON FACTORS INFLUENCING INDIVIDUAL INVESTORS' DECISIONS IN SELECTED COMMERCIAL PRIVATE BANKS IN KANO CITY OF NIGERIA

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Abstract

Investment decisions have obtained prominence outstanding to the g-eneral rise in employment opportunities and economic development of a nation. This research paper determines the study on various factors influencing investment decisions of individual investors in the Kano city centre of commerce in Nigeria. The structured questionnaire included more items that belong to some categories, namely, self-image; accounting information; neutral information; advocate recommendation; personal financial needs and general information. From the considerable literature evaluation, it was found that there are no single factors which influence the investment decisions of an individual. Moreover factors influencing investment decisions are determined by profit percentage, high returns, safety, influences of friends, risk diversification and so an. the personal financial needs, accounting information, general information is heavily influenced by the investors in the Kano state of Nigeria. Remaining the self-image, neutral information, and advocate recommendation is not affected more. It was proposed that the investment path must consider all the variables and its influences on the investor investment decisions.

Keywords: Investment decision, Factors influences, Investment types, knowledge, Investor Behaviour, Attitude

Introduction

Speculation choices are made by financial specialists and venture directors. Financial specialists regularly perform speculation investigation by utilizing essential examination, specialized examination and judgment. Venture choices are frequently bolstered by choice devices. It is accepted that data structure and the components in the private commercial banks efficiently impact people's investment choices just as trend results. Investors showcase conduct gets from mental standards of dynamic to clarify why individuals purchase or sell stocks. These variables will centre upon how financial specialists decipher and follow up on data to settle on venture choices. Social fund is characterized by Shefrin, (2000) as "a quickly developing region that manages the impact of brain science on the conduct of monetary professionals". Singular speculations conduct is worried about decisions about acquisition of little measures of protections for their own record (Nofsinger and Richard, 2002). Regardless of how much a financial specialist is very much educated, has done research, concentrated profoundly about the stock before contributing, he additionally carries on unreasonably with

the dread of misfortune later on. This diverse conduct in the individual financial specialists is brought about by different elements which bargain the speculator level headedness. An individual financial specialist is one who buys commonly modest quantities of protections for their own record.

Behavioural finance assumes that features of bank investment applicants and information structure analytically have an influence on individual's investor investment decisions. Within behavioural finance it is assumed that points of individuals investors and factors influencing investment decisions and return of Investment (ROI) as well. The focal point of behavioural finance is on the ways that people do explain and take action on information for creating investment decisions. There is a significant growth in the investment zone both in terms of volume and number of investors in Nigeria over the past span due to the deregulation of Nigerian financial sector. There is a change of various investment products with several options to attract the investors to invest. The number of regional stock exchanges has improved. Equity shares as an investment preference has come a long way from the mere higher dividend anticipations to the greater capital increase. The quality of ever-changing regulations, the payment guarantee by the depositories, Productive involvement of the Government, vibrant intermediaries and up to date technologically advanced exchanges, all have implanted a sense of assurance among the investors. Individual investors are normal people who are affected by factors of self-image, accounting information, neutral information, advocate recommendation, personal financial needs and general information factors. It can be opposed that investors make decisions intelligently but also depend on various factors.

Need for this study

This study helps to find out and identify the various factors influencing investment decisions among the individual investors. It facilitates to find whether the Investor guidelines must be made known to every investor/employee through their organization. Also, this study focuses on more awareness that is needed for the investors to make investments in various avenues. They must go for consultation before investing.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study about the opinion towards various factors influencing investment decisions among the investors.
2. To find out the most influential factors of investment decisions.
3. To suggest best investment opportunities in selected private commercial banks in Kano city of Nigeria.

Scope of the study

- The study focuses on finding the most prominent factor that influences individual investment decisions.
- This study is useful to identify the various influencing factors and decision-making process among the investors.

Limitations of the study

- This study has been conducted only for academic purpose, due to cost and time a comprehensive study not possible
- The sample size was restricted only 100, if it was increased many more varied answers as and suggestions would have been expected.
- The investors hesitate for conveying the true details about investment pattern could be a limitation
- The sample respondent feel difficult to fill the questionnaire and they do not like spent few minutes to give valuable responses on investment pattern and decisions so we restrict the sample size.

Reviews of literature

This part clarifies the discoveries by different scientists on venture choices. Social money has accomplished noteworthy walks in clarifying the social parts of venture choices. Social money explores decisions under vulnerability.

Theory of Mental Accounting expresses that people tend to put specific occasions into mental compartments, and the distinction between these compartments now and again impacts our conduct more than the occasions themselves. A contributing case of mental bookkeeping is best shown by the faltering to sell a venture that once had colossal increases and now has a humble addition. During a financial blast and positively trending market, individuals get familiar with sound, though paper, gains. At the point when the market revision empties financial specialist's total assets, they're increasingly reluctant to sell at the littler overall revenue. They make mental compartments for the additions they once had, making them sit tight for the return of that profitable period (Thaler, 2001).

Theory of over confidence says that individuals for the most part rate themselves as being better than expected in their capacities. They additionally overestimate the accuracy of their insight and their insight comparative with others. Numerous financial specialists accept they can reliably time the market. In any case, as a general rule there's a staggering measure of proof that demonstrates something else. Pomposity brings about overabundance exchanges, with exchanging costs imprinting benefits, (Tapia and Yermo, 2007).

Ambrose Jagongo (2014) Singular ventures conduct is worried about decisions about acquisition of modest quantities of protections for his or on the other hand her own record. Venture choices are regularly upheld by choice devices. It is expected that data structure and the elements in the market efficiently impact people's venture choices just as showcase results. The target of the investigation was to set up the components impacting speculation choices at the Nairobi Stock Exchange. The investigation was directed on the 42 financial specialists out of 50 speculators that established the test size. To gather information the analyst utilized an organized survey that was by and by directed to the respondents. The poll comprised 28 things. The respondents were the individual financial specialists. In this study, information was broken down utilizing frequencies, mean scores, standard deviations, rates, Friedman's test and Factor examination strategies. The scientist affirmed that there is by all

accounts a specific level of connection between the elements that conduct account hypothesis and past experimental proof recognized as the for the normal value financial specialist. The specialist discovered that the most significant elements that impact singular venture choices were: notoriety of the firm, association's status in industry, anticipated corporate income, benefit and condition of proclamation, past execution firms stock, cost per share, feeling on the economy and expected isolation by financial specialists. The discoveries from this exploration would give a comprehension of the different choices to be made by financial specialists dependent on the common elements and the possible results for every choice and would recognize the most impacting factors on the organization's financial specialists conduct on how their future arrangements and procedures will be influenced since venture choices by the financial specialists will decide the organization's system to be applied.

Jeet Singh and Preeti Yadav (2016) the current investigation attempts to discover the components that have significant impact on the offer of speculation choices of an example of 100 financial specialists in Moradabad city of Uttar Pradesh. Transformation in the fund business is achieved through the coming and development of social funds. Financial specialists scarcely act soundly in taking choices while contributing. Financial specialists essentially respond to the accessible data controlled by them and respond as needs be Loads of thought is required to be managed before putting resources into the value advertised. Proportion investigation is required to be thought of as a Specialized and money related investigation of the organization alongside the central examination of the economy is to be considered while putting resources into the capital market. The present paper attempts to discover the impression of male and female financial specialists with respect to different contemplations to be remembered while putting resources into the value advertised. The paper attempts to pack the demeanour of male and female financial specialists towards an assortment of venture choices. The analysts have chosen 60 male financial specialists and 40 female financial specialists from Jaipur and Moradabad urban areas. The investigation utilizes autonomous t-test, mean scores to test the theory. The paper presumes that financial specialists ought to quite far attempt to make basic, specialized and money related investigation before putting resources into the offers. Financial specialists whether male or female, ought to glance at all roads while putting their assets in various resources. Financial specialists should glance at all roads while contributing their assets. A few ventures are hazardous and some are not, so according to the time of financial specialists they ought to choose hazardous or less dangerous ventures. S.Hemalatha (2019) the motivation behind speculation is to increase gainful returns by putting away cash. An assortment of venture roads are accessible to people fixed store, protection approaches, government protections, corporate securities, Shares and common reserve, genuine bequests, items, chit reserves, post office plans, interest in gold and silver. A different component impacts the venture choice of the person. Segment profile too assumes an essential job in venture choice of the person. Along these lines, this investigation intends to discover attitude differences in the impression of singular speculators on factors impacting venture choice on the premise demographic profile of the people. The overview was gathered from 374 people in Chennai, Tamil Nadu. Illustrative measurements (t-test and f-test) are utilized to discover the estimation of mean,

standard deviation, standard blunder, mean of factors impacting singular venture choice. The outcomes discovered that variables of determination of venture shifts as indicated by sex, age, occupation, utilization of web, level of PC information, use of web-based exchanging

Research Methodology

This study belongs to descriptive in nature and explain the influencing factors and investment decision in the investors' perspective. This research study has conducted through empirical research in the field of investment opportunities in selected private commercial banks.

Study area: In and around Kano city (Centre of Commerce)

Sample Size

The sample frame in this study was selected randomly. A total number of 100 respondents were contacted and was given the opportunity to participate in the survey. In this study the survey design consists of a questionnaire distributed to the respondents. A statistical method is used to regulate the sample to confirm that the size of the sample is representable for the whole population.

Questionnaire Design

The five-point Likert scale was selected because of the response way for the questionnaire. For each of the dimensions, the respondents are examined to inform whether or not and the way strongly they agree or ignore the statement that's created. The responses were given scores e.g. from 1 to 5 in this analysis. Then the scores are summed up for each of the respondents so as to present an attitudinal score for every question.

Data Collection:

Primary data: It was collected by survey method by distributing the questionnaire to investors.

Secondary data collected through journals magazines, newspapers and CBN bulletins.

Tools for data analysis:

The data collected from the sources are analysed and interpreted in a systematic manner with the support of statistical tool SPSS.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Details of Respondents

S. No	Variables	Responses	No of Respondents	Total
1	No of Respondents	Male	95	100
		Female	05	
2	Age	Less Than 30	4	100
		30-40	48	
		40-50	40	
		Above 50	8	
3	Education Qualification	Schooling	15	100
		Degree	60	
		Master degree	25	
4	Occupation	Business	18	100
		Profession	34	
		Service	19	
		Retired	8	
		Others	21	
5	Annual Income	Less than 2 million ₦	20	100
		2 million to 5 million-₦	34	
		5 million to 10 million-₦	37	
		Above 10 million ₦	9	

Table2. Mean of Perception of Respondents

S. No	Variables	N	Mean	SD
1	Past Dividends	100	4.09	.830
2	Financial Ratio	100	3.81	.907
3	Recent Financial Performance	100	4.09	.889
4	Bonus	100	3.79	.782
5	Daily Reports	100	3.97	.915
6	Management & Directors of the company	100	3.92	.918
7	Ownership Structure of the Company	100	4.13	.787
8	Advice of the friends	100	4.33	.817
9	Family Culture in share investments	100	3.9	.813
10	Motivation by the people who are successful in share investment	100	4.06	.0851

ANOVA analysis

Education VS Investment factors

H₀: There is no significant difference between education and investment factors.

H₁: There is a significant difference between education and investment factors.

This section tries to measure the difference between education and investment factors by using ANOVA.

Table 3: F-test

S.NO	FACTORS	F	Sig.
1	Self-image	.782	.714
2	Accounting information	5.578	.005
3	Neutral information	1.151	.330
4	Advocate recommendation	.370	.957
5	Personal financial needs	8.739	.000
6	General information	.649	.834

Inference

From the above table shows the value of factor F and factor significant. It is clear from the table that self- image, neutral information, advocate recommendation, general information significant value is >0.05%. Hence accept null hypothesis i.e. there is no significance difference between education and factors. The accounting information & personal financial needs significant value is <0.05%. Hence accept alternative hypothesis i.e. there is a significant difference between education and factors.

Age VS Investment factors

H₀: There is no significant difference between age and investment factors.

H₁: There is a significant difference between age and investment factors.

This section tries to measure the difference between age and investment factors by using ANOVA.

Table4. F- Test

S.NO	FACTORS	F	Sig.
1	Self-image	8.739	.000
2	Accounting information	.7314	.0001
3	Neutral information	2.204	.016
4	Advocate recommendation	1.375	.205
5	Personal financial needs	3.911	.023
6	General information	15.382	.000

Inference

From the above table shows the value of factor F and factor significant. It is clear from the table that self-image, accounting information, neutral information, personal financial needs & general information significant value is $<0.05\%$. Hence accept alternative hypothesis i.e. there is significance difference between age and these factors. Advocate recommendation significant value is $>0.05\%$ hence accept null hypothesis i.e. there is no significance difference between age and advocate recommendation factors.

Correlation Analysis

H₀: There is no positive relationship among self-image factors, accounting information factors, neutral information factors, advocate recommendation factors, personal financial needs factors and general information factors.

H₁: There is a positive relationship among self-image factors, accounting information factors, neutral information factors, advocate recommendation factors, personal financial needs factors and general information factors.

Analysis of factors using Correlation

Table5. Correlation analysis

		IV1	IV2	IV3	IV4	IV5	DV
IV1	Pearson Correlation	1	-.137	.226*	.214*	.165	.129
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.175	.024	.032	.100	.202
	N	100	100	100	100	100	100
IV2	Pearson Correlation	-.137	1	.057	.202*	.084	.301**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.175		.572	.044	.406	.002
	N	100	100	100	100	100	100
IV3	Pearson Correlation	.226*	.057	1	.439**	.279**	.344**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.024	.572		.000	.005	.000
	N	100	100	100	100	100	100
IV4	Pearson Correlation	.214*	.202*	.439**	1	.270**	.226*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.032	.044	.000		.007	.024
	N	100	100	100	100	100	100
IV5	Pearson Correlation	.165	.084	.279**	.270**	1	.394**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.100	.406	.005	.007		.000
	N	100	100	100	100	100	100
DV	Pearson Correlation	.129	.301**	.344**	.226*	.394**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.202	.002	.000	.024	.000	
	N	100	100	100	100	100	100

Inference:

Table shows the value of r and its significant level. It is clear from table that significant value is $<0.05\%$ for self-image factors, accounting information factors, neutral information factors, advocate recommendation factors, personal financial needs factors and general information factors.

There is positive relationship between accounting factors and general information factors, neutral information factors and advocate recommendation factors, neutral information factors and personal financial needs factors, general information factors and neutral information factors, personal financial needs factors and general information factors,

It is also clear from table that the significant value is $>0.05\%$ for self-image factors, accounting information factors, neutral information factors, advocate recommendation factors, personal financial needs factors and general information factors.

There is a negative relationship between self-image factors and accounting information factors, self-image factors and neutral information factors, self-image factors and advocate recommendation factors, self-image factors and personal financial needs factors, self-image factors and general information factors, advocate recommendation factors and accounting information factors, advocate recommendation factors and personal financial needs factors, advocate recommendation factors and general information factors, personal financial needs factors and self-image factors, personal financial needs factors and accounting information factors.

Results and discussion

From frequency analysis

Majority of the respondents (investors) are male (95%) few of them female (5%).

Majority of the respondents (investors) are below 30 years (4%) followed by 30 to 40 years (48), 40 to 50 (40%) above 50 years (8%).

Majority of the respondents (investors) are UG (60%) followed by PG (25%), school (15%),

Majority of the respondents (investors) are 5 million ₦ to 10million ₦ (37%), followed by 2million ₦ to 5million ₦ (34%), >2million ₦ (20%), above 10million ₦ (9%).

Majority of the respondents are shares (26%), followed by bank deposits (20%), real estate (18%), mutual funds (17%), insurance plans (12%), and bonds (7%).

Majority of the respondents investment horizons are 1-2years (42%), followed by 6-12months (27%), 2-3years (19%), more than 3years (11%).

Majority of the respondents are tax saving (39%), wealth creation (34%), earn returns (19%) and future expenses (8%).

Majority of the respondents are low risk (42%) followed by safety of principal (24%), high returns (22%), maturity period (12%).

From Mean analysis

Financial firm investment product variables has the highest mean value 2.9500 followed by commercial bank investment, firm involvement, rich, firm status, feelings on the economy, perceived ethics, reputation of the firm.

The dividends paid variable has the highest value of mean 2.9300 followed by corporate earnings, past performance, price of a share, expected dividends, corporate position.

The statement of government variables has the highest value of the mean 2.7800 followed by information, fluctuation, coverage, economic indicators, and price fluctuation.

The statement of people opinion has the highest value of mean 2.6500 followed by broker recommendation, friends, and family member opinion.

The need of diversification has the highest value of the mean 2.7500 followed by attractiveness, false, minimizing risk.

The statement of location has the highest value of mean 2.5500 followed by diversify the risks, unsecured investment, tax benefits, favorable political situation, and nature of the industry.

From ANOVA test

There is no significance difference between education and self-image factors, education and neutral information factors, education and advocate recommendation factors, significance difference between age and neutral information factors, age and advocate recommendation factors

There is significance difference between education and accounting information factors, education and personal financial factors, education and general information factors, age and self-image factors, age and accounting information factors, age and personal financial factors, age and general information factors.

There is no significance difference between.

From Correlation analysis

There is positive relationship between accounting factors and general information factors, neutral information factors and advocate recommendation factors, neutral information factors and personal financial needs factors, general information factors and neutral information factors, advocate recommendation factors and neutral information factors, personal financial needs factors and general information factors, general information factors and personal financial needs.

There is negative relationship between self-image factors and accounting information factors, self-image factors and neutral information factors, self-image factors and advocate recommendation factors, self-image factors and personal financial needs factors, self-image factors and general information factors, accounting information factors and self-image factors, accounting information factors and neutral information factors, personal financial

needs factors and self-image factors, personal financial needs factors and accounting information factors, personal financial needs factors and advocate recommendation factors, general information factors and self-image factors, general information factors and advocate recommendation factors.

Suggestions

- The federal government of Nigeria has to arrange for investment awareness program to investors so, they can invest more.
- On account of this investors awareness program every investor increase knowledge so they are will be able to choose right investment decisions.
- A right investment decision leads to rise the economic growth.
- Economic growth of the nation invites more investors towards investments.
- People should be educated on the topic of the investment practices.
- Investors must be given direction about dividend investment in the shares.
- All the variables are somewhat moving the decision making behaviour of investor and accounting information set of variables is most influencing while advocate recommendation is the least influencing category of investors.
- Behavioural finance offers many suitable perceptions for investment professionals and thus, provides a framework for estimating active investment strategies for the investors.
- Since conduct account is another and promising part of money, monetary counsels should filter the conduct of financial specialists and their inclinations especially the urban speculators when exchanging common assets, stocks and putting resources into other money related choices.
- Speculators ought to quite far attempt to make principal, specialized and money related investigation before putting resources into the offers.
- The two kinds of financial specialists, male and female attempt to put resources into various resource classes.
- There are a few ventures which are hazardous and few are not, so relying on the age, the financial specialists they ought to choose about the level of hazard to be taken.
- More seasoned financial specialists ought to keep away from dangerous speculations while younger generation speculators can face challenge.

Conclusion

Behavioural finance is gaining strong reflection in financial research now-a-days. It designates that an individual's investment decision is not created on a certain factor further which is caused by more than one factor. Every individual is different from others essential to a number of factors which contain demographic factors such as age and gender, education level, social and economic background - self image of the firm, firm related information, advocate recommendation, personal financial needs and general information are measured before investors invest their money. The most testing experiment challenged by them is the

investment decision; they act in a logical manner and generally follow their requests and emotional subjectivity while making investment decisions. From the several literatures it is initiated that there is no single variable or factor which causes the investment decisions of an individual investors, it differs from person to person, place to place, securities to securities etc. This research completes that the individual investor's investment decision rests on how the obtainable information is being drawn-out to them and how much they are subject to taking risk while making decisions; thus each flexible of the factors playing an important role in influencing the investment style of an investor.

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